

Participant's consent (the DTA project)

 Mandatory questions are marked with an asterisk (*)

DigiTala in action - automatic speaking assessment supporting integration (DTA for short) is a project between University of Helsinki, Aalto University and University of Jyväskylä. The project is funded by the Research Council of Finland. I have been asked to participate in the DTA research project.

I have received sufficient information about

- The research and its purpose,
- What data* will be collected,
- How the data will be used in the research,
- How the data (speech data, surveys) will be processed and stored.

*Data = speech data and surveys (gender, age, mother tongue, other languages, study history, opinions on the speaking tasks)

By filling this form, I confirm that

- I have received [the privacy notice](#).
- I have received the [information sheet for research participants](#).
- I understand that participation in this research is voluntary. I have the right to discontinue participation in the research at any time.

Contact information

1. Name and contact information

Will not be given outside the research project and will only be used for research-related communication.

First name

Surname

Email *

Educational institution (school) *

Consent

2. I consent to participate in the DTA project. *

- I agree.
- I do not agree.

4. I may be contacted when follow-up on the research is planned (possible feedback, interviews). *

- I give permission
- I do not give permission

5. My data (speech data and surveys, not name or email) may be used by the project team members for research or educational purposes for teachers and raters. *

- I give permission
- I do not give permission

6. The data (speech data and surveys, not name or email) may be permanently stored in the Language Bank of Finland or similar trusted data archive and it may be used in other research related to language learning. *

Participation in the study does not require that you give permission to store your material in the Language Bank.

- I give permission
- I do not give permission